

Case Report: Siddha Treatment for Seronegative Rheumatoid Arthritis (RA)

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Abstract:

Background: In Siddha literature, Rheumatoid Arthritis (RA) is referred to as Vali Azhal Keel Vayu (VAKV). **Case Report:** A 51-year-old female presented with symptoms indicative of rheumatoid arthritis, including joint pain (especially in the hands, knees, and feet), exacerbated in the morning and after periods of inactivity, joint stiffness making daily activities difficult, swelling and tenderness in affected joints, fatigue, and malaise for the past six months. Laboratory investigations revealed elevated C-Reactive Protein (CRP) and a negative rheumatoid factor, indicating seronegative RA. The patient's disease severity was evaluated using the Rheumatoid Arthritis Severity Scale (RASS) and Disease Activity Score (DAS). This report emphasizes the importance of proper medication for seronegative RA, focusing on Siddha management with internal medicines (analgesic and anti-inflammatory Siddha drugs) and Vāta kēcari tailam for external therapeutic massage and fomentation to reduce pain and inflammation. She chose Siddha medicine as her primary treatment due to its holistic approach and minimal side effects. **Conclusion:** The intervention of Siddha medicine can potentially reduce seronegative rheumatoid arthritis. This approach could significantly impact by reducing inflammation rates and surgeries, improving the overall quality of life, and lowering the economic burden of treating RA.

Keywords: Vali Azhal Keel Vayu, Joint pain, Integrative management, Siddha medicine

Introduction:

Rheumatoid arthritis (RA) is a long-term, inflammatory condition that affects the joints and has a worldwide prevalence of approximately 5 cases per 1,000 adults. It predominantly impacts women, who are 2 to 3 times more likely to develop RA compared to men, though it can onset at any age¹. Rheumatoid arthritis affects about 0.39% to 1% of the population, ranking it among the most common chronic inflammatory diseases². RA is marked by symmetrical joint pain, swelling, and stiffness, which often result in progressive joint damage and disability. This condition significantly affects life expectancy, as RA patients face a roughly 50% higher risk of premature death. On average, their life expectancy is shortened by 3 to 10 years compared to the general population^{3,4}. Notably, RA affects around 0.8% of the population and does so without any racial bias⁵. Diagnosing seronegative RA can be difficult due to the absence of traditional biomarkers. To improve diagnosis, researchers have investigated potential biomarkers, such as serum antibodies against disease-associated proteins like carbamylated proteins and peptidyl-arginine deiminase type 4. These biomarkers have successfully identified 23%–36% of patients with seronegative RA, offering valuable tools for more accurate diagnosis and management of the condition⁶.

According to Yugi and Theraiyar in Siddha medicine, various factors contribute to the development of Vatha diseases. These factors include the excessive consumption of bitter, pungent, and astringent foods, disrupted sleep patterns, excessive physical activity during summer, frequent fasting, and carrying heavy weights. Vatha diseases are extensive, with literature identifying 80 different types. One specific type, Vali Azhal Keel Vayu (VAKV), closely mirrors the signs and symptoms of rheumatoid arthritis. Siddha medicine categorizes Keel Vayu into ten types, further grouped into three major divisions: Vali Keel Vayu, Azhal Keel Vayu, and Aiya Keel Vayu. The Siddha system's approach to pain management is notably unique, offering 32 types of external therapeutic care, including Varmam⁷⁻⁹.

This case report highlights the successful management of rheumatoid arthritis through Siddha medicine. It details the case of a patient with seronegative rheumatoid arthritis who was effectively treated using both internal and external Siddha therapeutic approaches.

Declaration of the Patient Consent

The authors confirm that they have obtained all necessary written informed consent from the patient for the publication of this case report and the accompanying images.

Case Study

A fifty-one-year-old female from Vellore, Tamil Nādu, visited the Outpatient Department of Aadhara Healthcare Siddha Hospital, Vellore, on August 12, 2021. She complained of knee joint pain, pain in both legs and ankle joints, joint stiffness, swelling, and tenderness in the affected joints. These symptoms had persisted for six months, hindering her daily activities. She had been diagnosed with seronegative rheumatoid arthritis at an orthopaedic hospital and had received treatment there from January 2021 to March 2021. There was no relevant family history of rheumatoid arthritis, and she had experienced menopause at 47 without any gynaecological symptoms. She was not taking any concomitant medication for her current complaints but had a history of type 2 diabetes mellitus since 2020, managed separately.

After a thorough examination, it was decided that Siddha treatment would be appropriate. Prior to starting this therapy, the patient underwent diagnostic assessments to

gauge the severity and activity of her rheumatoid arthritis (RA). The Rheumatoid Arthritis Severity Scale (RASS) was used, scoring approximately 234 out of 300, indicating severe disease impact. The Disease Activity Score (DAS) was also calculated, resulting in a value of around 5.5. In August 2021, comprehensive laboratory investigations supported the clinical diagnosis. Blood tests revealed elevated levels of C-reactive protein (CRP), an inflammatory marker associated with active RA. The rheumatoid factor test returned negative, indicating seronegative RA. X-rays showed narrowing of joint spaces, reflecting cartilage loss and joint erosion, confirming the diagnosis of RA.

Based on these assessments, Siddha treatment was recommended. The patient underwent a 90-day Siddha treatment regimen supervised by our team, which included internal and external therapeutic modalities tailored to her condition. The treatment plan included Siddha herbal formulations administered orally, such as Racakanti meḷuku (RGM), Tirikaṭuku cūraṇam (TKC), Amukkarā cūraṇam (AMKC), Caṅku paṛpam, Cilācattu paṛpam, Kuṅkiliya paṛpam, Paṭika pūṅkāvi, Veṭi aṇṇapēti Centūram, Tiripalā cūraṇam (TPC), and cīraka cūraṇam. External management involved Tokkaṇam (therapeutic massage) using Vāta kēcari tailam accompanied by Orraṭam (fomentation) on affected joints. The patient was also advised to engage in Yoga and breathing exercises daily.

On the 90th day of treatment, blood samples showed significant improvements. Pain assessments using RASS indicated a reduction from 75 to 2.5 on the DAS, signifying complete pain relief. The positive outcomes led to the continuation of similar treatment protocols during the follow-up period. During the subsequent month of follow-up, the patient reported no recurrence of symptoms and no adverse effects from either the initial treatment or the follow-up regimen. Overall, the combined Siddha treatment approach proved effective in alleviating the patient's condition, as evidenced by the substantial reduction in pain scores and the absence of recurrence during the follow-up phase.

Days	Treatment and Observation
Visit 0 (12 th Aug 2021)	The patient came to the OPD and completed her consultation. Blood investigations revealed an elevated CRP level of 17.89 mg/L, a RASS (Rheumatoid Arthritis Severity Scale) score of 234, and a DAS (Disease Activity Score) of 5.5. Akastiyar kuḷampu (200 mg) was administered in the morning as a single dose with ginger juice for purgation therapy to regulate the Mukkurram (three humors).
Visit 1 (14 th Aug 2021)	The patient reported passing loose stools 5-6 times without abdominal pain. Within 2-3 hours, she resumed regular bowel movements, and the regular management regimen was started: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Racakanti meḷuku– 500 mg twice a day with palm jaggery. 2. Mixture medicines: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Amukkarā cūraṇam – 2 gm - Tirikaṭuku cūraṇam – 2 gm - Caṅku paṛpam – 200 mg - Cilācattu paṛpam – 200 mg - Paṭika pūṅkāvi – 100 mg - Kuṅkiliya paṛpam – 200 mg twice a day 3. Tiripalā cūraṇam – 1 gm twice a day with warm water. 4. Cīraka cūraṇam – 1 gm six times a day with hot water. 5. Vāta kēcari tailam – 5 to 10 ml for external application on the affected area daily. External management is performed using

	<p>therapeutic massage with Vāta kēcari tailam, accompanied by fomentation on the affected joints during each visit. The patient's condition was monitored with the following results:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RASS (Rheumatoid Arthritis Severity Scale): 200 • DAS (Disease Activity Score): 5.0
Visit 2 (30 th Aug 2021)	<p>The patient reported slight reductions in pain, swelling, and tenderness. She was advised to follow a balanced Vali diet, with specific food preferences and restrictions:</p> <p>Preferential Foods:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Boiled food and vegetable soups - Flax seeds - Almonds - Spinach - Walnut - Soybean - Chia seeds - Milk <p>Non-Preferential Foods:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cold food and drinks - Potato - Banana - Lima beans - Black-eyed beans - Bulbous root/tubers - Raw or uncooked products <p>She was instructed to follow this diet regularly to help manage her condition.</p>
Visit 3 (13 th Sep 2021)	<p>The patient was confirmed to be following the diet and medications properly. She reported moderate reductions in pain, joint stiffness, swelling, and tenderness in the affected joints. She was able to perform daily activities with less pain compared to before. She was advised to continue adhering to both the medications and the diet as prescribed.</p>
Visit 4 (27 th Sep 2021)	<p>The patient experienced a significant reduction in pain in her knees, ankles, and fingers. She reported being able to walk without pain and comfortably stretch and fold her arms and legs. Blood samples were collected for further investigation to monitor her progress.</p>
Visit 5 (12 th Oct 2021)	<p>Blood investigations revealed a significant reduction in CRP levels, and radiographic images showed decreased cartilage loss and joint erosions. The patient was advised to continue with the prescribed medications and diet, and to incorporate gentle yoga postures and breathing exercises to enhance flexibility and reduce stress. The updated assessments were:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RASS (Rheumatoid Arthritis Severity Scale): 75 • DAS (Disease Activity Score): 2.5
Follow up-1 (27 th October 2021)	<p>No recurrence of symptoms was observed.</p>

Biochemical Parameters	Before Treatment	After Treatment
C-Reactive protein	17.89 mg/L	9.44 mg/L

Measuring Scale	Before Treatment	After Treatment
RASS (Rheumatoid Arthritis Severity Scale)	234	75
DAS (Disease Activity Score)	5.5	2.5

Discussion

A fifty-one-year-old female from Vellore, Tamil Nadu, presented to the Outpatient Department with joint pain primarily in her hands, knees, and feet. Her symptoms included intensified pain in the morning and after periods of inactivity, joint stiffness that hindered daily activities, swelling and tenderness in the affected joints, as well as fatigue and malaise, persisting for the past six months.

She underwent a 90-day Siddha treatment regimen supervised by our team, utilizing a comprehensive approach that combined internal and external therapeutic modalities tailored to her condition. While analgesics and anti-inflammatory drugs are commonly used for arthritis management, Siddha treatments were recommended in this case to alleviate her symptoms and enhance her quality of life.

The treatment plan included:

Internal Therapeutic Modalities:

- Racakanti meḷuku
- Tirikaṭuku cūraṇam
- Amukkarā cūraṇam
- Caṅku paṇṇam
- Cilācattu paṇṇam
- Kuṅkiliya paṇṇam
- Paṭika pūṅkāvi
- Veṭi aṇṇapēti Centūram
- Tiripalā cūraṇam
- cīraka cūraṇam

External Therapeutic Modalities:

- Tokkaṇam (therapeutic massage) using Vāta kēcari tailam
- Orraṭam (fomentation) on affected joints

Additionally, the patient was advised to incorporate Yoga and breathing exercises into her daily routine. Vāta kēcari tailam is a commonly used Siddha external medicine that helps reduce joint stiffness and improve circulation. Orraṭam (fomentation) involves the application

of heat packs or warm herbal poultices to alleviate pain and inflammation in the affected joints. Gentle yoga postures and breathing exercises are recommended to improve flexibility and reduce stress.

Racakanti meḷuku (RGM) is recognized for its anti-inflammatory and analgesic properties. Additionally, the Siddha system of medicine has demonstrated its utility in managing HIV, with scientific research involving viral load assays and CD4+/CD8+ ratios providing evidence of its effectiveness¹⁰. The herbal ingredients in Racakanti meḷuku (RGM) have shown various beneficial properties, including anti-tumor, anticancer, antioxidant, detoxification, and immunomodulatory effects¹¹. Tirikaṭuku cūraṇam (TKC) helps reduce joint inflammation and stiffness. It has demonstrated significant anti-inflammatory activity, with an IC-50 value of 83.93 µg/ml, indicating its effectiveness in stabilizing Red Blood Cells (RBC) membranes. Tirikaṭuku cūraṇam (TKC) is also used to treat digestive disorders, including indigestion, dyspepsia, flatulence, and intermittent fever^{12, 13}. Amukkarā cūraṇam (AMKC) enhances immunity and provides overall strength. It is traditionally used to manage arthritic pain, particularly in the treatment of chikungunya¹⁴. Amukkarā cūraṇam (AMKC) exhibits high anti-inflammatory activity, with an IC-50 of 35.19 µg/ml for RBC membrane stabilization. A study by Singh S. et al. reported that AMKC achieved a maximum inhibition of 70.89% at 500 µg/ml, compared to Diclofenac sodium's 94.74% at 100 µg/ml. AMKC significantly rejuvenates tissues and provides anti-arthritic benefits, making it particularly useful for managing rheumatoid arthritis.¹⁵⁻¹⁷. Caṅku paṇṇam demonstrates mild inhibitory action against bacteria such as *E. coli*, *Klebsiella*, *Proteus*, *Pseudomonas*, and *Staphylococcus*. It shows 38.3% acute anti-inflammatory activity and 27.8% chronic anti-inflammatory activity in albino rats, along with mild analgesic effects.¹⁸. Tiripalā cūraṇam (TPC) exhibits strong anti-inflammatory properties, with an IC-50 of 24.00 µg/ml in stabilizing RBC membranes. This polyherbal formulation also shows anti-arthritic effects in the Complete Freund's Adjuvant-induced arthritis model. When administered, TPC significantly reduced biochemical and molecular changes in arthritic rats compared to indomethacin (3 mg/kg body weight), as confirmed by radiological and histopathological examinations. Additionally, TPC helps prevent bone and cartilage degradation associated with rheumatoid arthritis¹⁹⁻²¹. Inductively coupled plasma - optical emission spectrometry (ICP-OES) analysis of Cilācattu paṇṇam shows a calcium concentration of 456.342 mg/L. Calcium channel blockers are known to have anti-inflammatory properties. Calcium can suppress the production of platelet-aggregating factor in endothelial cells in a dose-dependent manner, which may contribute to its anti-inflammatory effects²²⁻²⁴. Kuṅkiliya paṇṇam contains phytochemicals such as ketones, resins, saponins, steroids, terpenes, tannins, and phenols. These compounds may delay or improve rheumatoid arthritis (RA) due to their antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, immunomodulatory, and enzymatic effects^{25, 26}.

In this case report, we explored a new combination regimen of Siddha medicines for rheumatoid arthritis, guided by evidence from Siddha literature. In the Siddha system, rheumatoid arthritis is classified under Vali nōykaḷ, which relates to Vali-type diseases. This Siddha regimen has substantial evidence supporting its anti-inflammatory, analgesic, and immunomodulatory effects. The patient experienced these beneficial effects from the Siddha regimen. Additionally, external pain management therapies from Siddha helped reduce the Vali Kurram in her body.

Conclusion

This case study underscores the efficacy of Siddha medicine in managing seronegative rheumatoid arthritis. The holistic approach of Siddha therapy, which includes internal medications, external therapies, and lifestyle modifications, led to substantial improvements in both symptoms and disease severity without significant adverse effects. The patient experienced notable relief from pain and inflammation, improved joint function, and an overall enhancement in quality of life. These positive outcomes highlight the potential of Siddha medicine as a complementary treatment for rheumatoid arthritis.

Given the encouraging results observed in this case, further research and clinical trials are warranted to validate the effectiveness and safety of Siddha medicine in the management of rheumatoid arthritis and other autoimmune conditions. Such studies could provide robust evidence to support the integration of Siddha practices into broader therapeutic protocols, offering patients a holistic and potentially more effective approach to managing chronic inflammatory diseases.

Limitation of the study

- **Lack of Control Group:** No control group for comparison, making it hard to confirm the regimen's efficacy.
- **Subjective Measures:** Improvements based on patient reports; objective clinical markers are needed.
- **Generalizability:** Results may not apply to all RA patients due to variability in disease and treatments.

Author Contribution

SG, SA, TR has conducted the study, data management and compilation report.

Conflict of Interest

No author does not have any conflict of interest.

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